

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF CFRP REINFORCED CONCRETE SLABS INCLUDING CFRP ANCHORS

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ABSTRACT

The flexural reinforcement of slabs with CFRP is a well-established retrofit technique; however, delamination continues to be the primary factor constraining the strength enhancement. Prior studies have demonstrated that CFRP anchors can effectively postpone delamination, yet the complete understanding of the influence of various design variables on these anchors remains limited. This paper introduces a numerical model for reinforced concrete slabs strengthened with CFRP plies and anchors. The three-dimensional model accurately represents the behavior of CFRP-reinforced slabs as tested by previous researchers (Smith, Zhang, & Wang, 2013).

KEYWORDS

Delamination delay; slab flexure strengthening; anchors; numerical simulation.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) composites have emerged as a well-established technology for retrofitting structural members. However, a significant limitation of this retrofit technique is the occurrence of premature and brittle debonding failure before reaching the full tensile strength. To address this issue, CFRP anchors have been introduced as an efficient method for preventing or delaying delamination. Although a comprehensive design guideline for CFRP anchors is yet to be established, current codes recognize their effectiveness in achieving higher strains in the CFRP retrofit system (ACI Committee 440.2R, 2017). Various finite element method (FEM) modeling techniques have been employed to simulate CFRP delamination (Coronado & Lopez, 2007; Kalfat & Al-Mahaidi, 2014, 2015; Lee & Lopez, 2019; Lu, Ye, Teng, & Jiang, 2005). However, only a few finite element models for CFRP anchors have successfully replicated past experiments (Al-Sammari & Breña, 2018; Sakin & Anil, 2019; Yang, Smith, Wang, & Lim, 2018). To date, no numerical model has been proposed specifically for CFRP anchors in slab applications, explicitly considering the behavior of the anchors.

The current paper introduces a finite element method (FEM) model for slabs reinforced with CFRP plies and anchors, which were subjected to flexural loading in previous studies conducted by Smith et al. (2013). These slabs were tested with a four-point load distribution, generating a constant moment zone at the middle of the slab. The failure mode observed in these slabs was characterized by intermediate crack-induced debonding (IC debonding), which refers to debonding occurring at the midspan of the beam due to flexural or flexural-shear cracking away from the plate ends (Teng, Smith, Yao, & Chen, 2003). The presented model successfully captures the behavior of the control slab (S2.1), slab with CFRP plies only (S2.2), and slab with both CFRP plies and anchors (S2.5), as observed in the experimental program by Smith et al. (2013). However, the current study does not include modeling of other slabs that involved variations in CFRP anchor's dowel inclination, sizes, distribution, and fan direction.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

The tridimensional model of the CFRP-reinforced slabs was created using Atena Science software (Cervenka, Cervenka, & Pukl, 2002). To expedite the analysis, only one quarter of the beam was modeled due to the problem's double symmetry. As depicted in Figure 1a, the slab's boundary conditions included displacement restrictions along the x and z axes to account for the double symmetry, as well as a point support on the bottom steel plate. The load was applied by downward displacement of the

middle point on the top steel plate. Steel plate supports were implemented to distribute the reactions over a larger concrete area and mitigate stress concentrations.

The concrete was divided into two sections: the first comprised coarse mesh elements with linear displacement interpolation between nodes, and the second consisted of fine mesh elements with quadratic displacement interpolation between nodes (Figure 1b). This differentiation was made to optimize computational time since there was no significant difference in global behavior when compared to using quadratic elements for all materials. As illustrated in Figure 1b, all materials near the CFRP reinforcements were modeled using quadratic elements. Coarse elements representing concrete and the steel plates were meshed with element sizes ranging from 10 to 25 mm, while finer elements near the CFRP plies and anchors were meshed with element sizes ranging from 3 to 8 mm. All solid elements consisted of isoparametric brick elements. A master-slave approach was employed when different mesh geometries intersected (Vladimir Cervenka, Libor Jedele, 2018).

Material Properties

Concrete

The fracture-plastic constitutive model CC3DNonLinCementitious2 (Vladimir Cervenka, Libor Jedele, 2018) was employed for modeling the behavior of concrete. The values for concrete compressive strength, modulus of elasticity, and tensile strength were based on the average reported values from the experimental program conducted by Smith et al. (2013). Other concrete parameters, such as the fracture energy, were obtained using empirical equations (Vos, 1983). From the experimental results, it was observed that there was a separation of approximately 100 mm between flexural cracks. This distance coincided with the spacing of the stirrups. Although this value was incorporated into the material properties as a maximum crack spacing, the explicit modelling of the transverse rebars also induced a similar crack distance. In order to prevent microcracking caused by the presence of anchors and fine meshed elements, a minimum distance of 20 mm between cracks, which is similar to the reported maximum aggregate size, was enforced in the model.

Steel

Longitudinal and transverse rebars, both with a nominal diameter of 10 mm, were modeled as elastic perfectly plastic linear elements with a perfect connection to their surrounding concrete elements. The modulus of elasticity (207 GPa) and the yield stress (515 MPa) were obtained from the experimental data reported by Smith et al. (2013). The support steel plates were modeled as linear elastic materials.

CFRP plies

The longitudinal plies of CFRP were modeled using a combination of three elements: an epoxy matrix, carbon fiber reinforcements, and thin interface elements between the epoxy and concrete surfaces. The epoxy matrix was represented as a linear elastic material with nominal properties provided by the manufacturer (Sika, 2018). Carbon fibers were simplified to a few linear reinforcement elements with equivalent cross-sectional areas and modeled as one-dimensional linear elastic elements up to the point of ultimate strength. The interface elements were modeled using the CC3DInterface material type, which accounts for both sliding and opening displacements (Vladimir Cervenka, Libor Jedele, 2018). These elements exhibit a Mohr-Coulomb failure surface with an ellipsoid in the tension regime.

A simplified empirical model (Lu, Teng, Ye, & Jiang, 2005) was employed to calibrate the parameters of the interface elements. It is important to note that this simplified empirical model is based on pure shear delamination tests of CFRP joints, and the most crucial parameter utilized in this model is the tensile strength of the concrete. However, delamination joint tests differ from slab tests in terms of the stress state of the concrete elements just beneath the CFRP. In joint tests, the concrete is typically under compression in the direction parallel to delamination, whereas in slabs, the concrete is subjected to tension. As a result, it was observed that using the nominal tensile strength of concrete overestimated the delamination strength of CFRP-reinforced slabs without anchors. Therefore, a value of 25% of the reported tensile strength was found to provide a suitable approximation for obtaining the load-deflection curve of the CFRP-reinforced slab without anchors. This approach was taken similar to the work of previous researchers in the case of shear CFRP retrofit (Qu & Lu, 2005).

CFRP anchors

Anchors were modeled as a combination of two elements: the dowel embedded within the concrete and the fan connected to the longitudinal plies. The dowel elements exhibit a perfect connection with the surrounding concrete. They are represented as a linear elastic matrix based on the epoxy properties and the carbon fibers modeled as smeared reinforcement in the direction of the dowel. The dowel elements near the longitudinal plies possess smeared reinforcement at a 45° angle to capture the behavior of carbon fiber bending. This approach was chosen due to the complex geometry in the distribution of carbon fibers in the bending zone near the anchor's surface. The fan is represented by discrete carbon fibers with an equivalent cross-sectional area directly connected to the longitudinal carbon fibers (Figure 1b).

(a) Boundary conditions of finite element model of specimen S5

(b) Finite element model materials of specimen S5

Figure 1: Finite element model description

It is important to note that the epoxy's modulus of elasticity was reported by the manufacturer after seven days of curing (Sika, 2018). However, the experimental program was conducted several months after construction, and the epoxy's modulus of elasticity was not tested on the day of slab testing. In the case of longitudinal plies, the effect of the epoxy's modulus of elasticity was not significant since the interface elements capture most of the delamination behavior. However, in the case of CFRP anchors,

using the reported seven-day modulus of elasticity results in a significant reduction in the strength increase attributed to the CFRP anchors. It was observed that a modulus of elasticity ten times greater than the reported seven-day value provided reasonable results when compared to the experiments. Beyond ten times the reported seven-day modulus, the effect on the strength of CFRP anchors diminishes significantly.

SOLUTION PROCEDURE

The model utilizes a static analysis with displacement control, employing the Newton-Raphson method. Previous studies have highlighted the significant impact of displacement step size on the bond response (Al-Saoudi, 2018; Kalfat & Al-Mahaidi, 2015). For instance, in pure shear delamination tests, a step size of 0.005 mm was determined to facilitate optimal convergence and capture the complete range of post-peak response and failure load (Kalfat, Al-Mahaidi, & Smith, 2013). In the present model, where the deflection displacement is applied perpendicular to the delamination direction, a larger step size of 0.03 mm was found to produce reasonable results without encountering convergence issues.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical model results are compared to the experimental results reported by Smith et al. (2013). Figures 2 to 4 display the total load versus midspan deflection of the investigated slabs (S2.1, S2.2, and S2.5). The same nomenclature as the reported experiments is utilized for the numerical models. The control slab S2.1, which lacks any CFRP reinforcement, exhibits a ductile behavior similar to that observed in the experiments. Figure 2 demonstrates that cracking initiates at a higher load in the model compared to the experiment; nevertheless, the maximum load is very close in both the model and the test. In both cases, the longitudinal reinforcement reaches its yield point at a deflection of approximately 10 mm.

Figure 2: Control slab (S2.1), load vs deflection curves

Figure 3 illustrates the load-deflection curves of slab S2.2, which consists of only longitudinal plies of CFRP without anchors. As explained previously, the strength contribution of the CFRP plies highly depends on the properties assigned to the interface elements. The parameters of these interface elements are derived from empirical closed-form equations that heavily rely on the concrete's tensile strength (f_t) in the elements beneath the CFRP reinforcement (Lu, Teng, et al., 2005). When using the reported uncracked tensile strength of concrete, the load tends to be overestimated, although the final deflection before delamination aligns closely with the experimental results. Since the primary objective of the proposed model is to predict strength increments, the S2.1 model was calibrated to achieve a maximum load value that closely matches the experimental results. Concrete elements near the CFRP plies experience tension due to the flexion of the slab, reducing the tensile strength of these elements in the model. Consequently, a reduction to 25% of f_t was deemed appropriate to obtain a similar maximum

load in the CFRP reinforced slab without anchors. Figure 3 demonstrates that the model tends to exhibit higher stiffness in the load-deflection curve compared to the experiments after the initial cracking. However, once the longitudinal rebars yield, the model's stiffness closely resembles that of the experiments. After delamination occurs, the load-deflection curve returns to a state similar to the case without CFRP, which is consistent with the experimental findings. For the sake of computational efficiency, the analysis was terminated a few steps after delamination.

Figure 3: CFRP slab (S2.2), load vs deflection curves

The load-deflection curves for the slab with CFRP anchors are presented in Figure 4. Up until the initiation of delamination (approximately at a 36 kN load), the behavior is slightly stiffer compared to the CFRP slab without anchors (Figure 3), as explained previously. The strength of the anchors is influenced by the elasticity modulus of the epoxy. Unfortunately, the experimental program did not report this value at the time of testing, which occurred several months after construction. The manufacturer only provided this value at a seven-day age of curing, which was 3489 MPa (Sika, 2018). It was observed that increasing the epoxy's elasticity modulus by a factor of ten resulted in a diminished influence on the strength increase. This sensibility analysis was developed for interface properties calculated with 25% of f_t .

Slab S2.3 was also modeled with interface elements calculated with a 100% of f_t , the results are also shown in Figure 4. Although for Slab 2.2 a better approximation was obtained when reducing f_t , for slabs with anchor a better approximation is obtained when using 100% of f_t . It is speculated this occurs because due to the delay in delamination produced by the CFRP anchors which also reduces concrete cracking and maintain its tensile strength. As shown in Figure 4 for specimen "FEM (Ex10)-100% f_t ", once the constant moment zone fully delaminates the stiffness in the model becomes lower than in the tests, however delamination propagation is delayed behind the first anchor. After delamination is complete a sudden drop in strength is observed, although the anchors alone continue to carry load. A second drop in strength is observed once the last three anchors rupture, the analysis was stopped after this point since the objective of the model is the prediction of the maximum load of the specimen.

The maximum load and corresponding deflection are lower in the model compared to the experiments. These conservative predictions are considered reasonable, as the objective of the model with CFRP anchors is to predict strength increase. Table 1 provides a summary of the maximum strengths attained prior to delamination in the examined slabs.

Figure 4: CFRP slab with anchors (S2.5), load vs deflection curves

Table 1: Summary of results

Specimen	Description	Max. Strength (kN)		EXP/FEM
		EXP	FEM	
S2.1	Control	22.68	22.25	1.02
S2.2	CFRP Plies	36.54	36.59	1.00
S2.5	CFRP Plies + CFRP Anchors	49.40	46.56	1.06

Figures 5 to 8 depict the behavior of slab S2.5 just before achieving full delamination. The failure mode is controlled by flexural cracks concentrated at the center of the slab, which propagate towards the end plates. Microcracks are observed around the anchor's dowels, along the CFRP longitudinal plies, and beneath the interface elements. Shear stresses of the interface elements can be observed in Figure 6. Despite CFRP anchors delaying delamination, it continues to progress until reaching the end plate. In the model, delamination below unruptured anchors still occurs. Figure 7 presents the concrete plastic strains, revealing that the concrete around the CFRP anchor's dowels exhibits higher plastic strains than the plastic strain at compressive strength (ϵ_{ps}^{cp}), suggesting that the concrete is being crushed. The longitudinal stresses in the x direction in the concrete are displayed in Figure 8. While most of the concrete experiences tension in this direction, the concrete around the anchors undergoes considerable compression stresses, comparable to the compressed fiber at the top of the slab.

Figure 5: Flexural cracks at maximum load before delamination (slab S2.5)

Figure 6: Shear stress of interface elements at maximum load before delamination (slab S2.5)

Figure 7: Plastic strain above ϵ_{ps}^{cp} , indicating concrete crushing, at maximum load before delamination (slab S2.5)

Figure 8: Longitudinal stresses on concrete at maximum load before delamination (slab S2.5)

CONCLUSIONS

The present research introduces a finite element method (FEM) model for RC slabs reinforced with CFRP plies and anchors. The FEM results exhibit a conservative correlation with the experimental findings. A static analysis with deformation control is employed in the model. The FEM analysis did not encounter any convergence issues, although a dynamic approach may yield even closer results to the experiments as the anchors approach failure. The inclusion of CFRP anchors leads to an increase in strength and a delay in delamination. The models presented in this paper will serve as a foundation for further parametric analysis, allowing for variations in the dowel's angle, anchor size, and location. Further study is required in the use of delamination models based on pure shear joint tests and their compatibility with flexural CFRP reinforcement with CFRP anchors.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.